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The Impact of the Chronic Care Model on Health Outcomes and Patient Satisfaction Among Elderly Patients: A Scoping Review

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Abstract

Background: Chronic diseases significantly impact the elderly, who require comprehensive care to minimize complications. The Chronic Care Model (CCM) offers a systematic approach to restructuring medical care, enhancing decision support, promoting self-management, improving clinical information for health systems, and providing better access to community resources.

Objective: This study aims to explore how chronic care management improves health outcomes for elderly patients.

Methodology: A scoping review was conducted to address two primary questions: "How does the Chronic Care Model (CCM) lead to satisfaction among elderly individuals with chronic conditions?" and "What roles do health providers play in the Chronic Care Model (CCM) to achieve such satisfaction?" Various databases were searched for relevant literature. Content thematic analysis was employed to gain a deeper understanding of predetermined themes, including the chronic care models, principles, and programs, their implementation, the role of nurses in executing and achieving the outcomes of these models, and patient outcomes such as satisfaction and experience.

Results: The review included 25 articles from various settings, regions, and countries. The findings confirmed the positive role of adopting the Chronic Care Model in enhancing patient experience and satisfaction in chronic care settings. Additionally, the study highlighted the crucial role of nurses in achieving desired patient outcomes, including clinical outcomes, high-quality care, and patient satisfaction.

Conclusion: Adopting the Chronic Care Model significantly enhances the satisfaction and experience of elderly adults. Further research is recommended to explore the adoption of CCM and its impact in developing countries.

Keywords: Chronic Care Model, Patient Satisfaction, Patient Outcomes, Elderly, Nurses

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Introduction

The leading cause of death in elderly patients is the continuous occurrence of infections and related complications, accounting for 63% of deaths, mainly when patients do not receive optimal care. Unfortunately, some patients report dissatisfaction with the care provided by healthcare providers, which negatively impacts their quality of life. To reduce high mortality rates, the healthcare system has introduced Chronic Care Management (CCM), a multidimensional framework for managing chronic diseases in patients with complex health issues. CCM aims to guide and

improve each patient's functional and clinical outcomes by involving patients and healthcare providers in a coordinated effort to manage chronic conditions and their complications.

Critical aspects of CCM include establishing a structured healthcare information system, such as Electronic Health Records (EHR), to track medications, allergies, and other relevant patient data. This system ensures that issues related to chronic illnesses are addressed medically and through effective communication between patients, healthcare workers,

and families. Patients and their families are often required to make lifestyle changes, and patients must be educated about the benefits of treatment and the risks of non-compliance to improve their overall condition.

According to Coleman and Brach (2009), the CCM model, developed over a decade ago, has been widely adopted by care facilities to enhance ambulatory care and overall clinical quality. The literature examining the effectiveness of CCM, through various studies published since 2000, supports its use as a framework for improving patient care, leading to better health outcomes and customer satisfaction. However, there is still work to be done in areas like cost-effectiveness. Older adults are particularly vulnerable to care gaps and errors due to potential transitions between healthcare facilities during illness, which can result in unnecessary hospitalizations or even death (Stellefson et al., 2013).

Healthcare providers are crucial in assisting elderly patients in transitioning smoothly between care settings by adopting a systematic approach and providing individualized care, enhancing patient and family satisfaction in hospitals and at home. A study by Cooper and McCarter (2013) evaluated the chronic care management program conducted by visiting nurses, assessing its impact on self-management knowledge and patient satisfaction with clinical measures. The study found that chronic disease self-management during home visits, supported by CCM, improved clinical indicators such as BMI, fasting blood sugar levels, blood pressure, and self-efficacy related to educational development (Cooper & McCarter, 2014).

Many older adults suffer from multiple chronic conditions, which can overwhelm patients and families and lead to dissatisfaction. To address this issue, healthcare facilities have implemented a triple-aim plan, which focuses on improving individual and population health and reducing healthcare costs. Wagner's chronic care model is often used to prevent and manage chronic diseases in elderly patients, as healthcare systems need to offer better services to this population (Drouin et al., 2015).

CCM is utilized in chronic care units and nursing homes and is particularly effective for patients diagnosed with multiple chronic diseases, such as respiratory illnesses, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and cancer (Endrline et al., 2013). The CCM model employs a systematic approach to minimize clinical care errors through collaboration between the community and the healthcare system. The study's goal was to describe how researchers applied the CCM in 16 articles focused on elderly care, and the results were positive, with recommendations to measure future satisfaction levels

for disease management and clinical decision-making.

The CCM comprises six elements: a health system based on goals and structures, community partnerships with resources, support for healthcare workers and patients through new evidence, self-management support through skills development, clinical information systems providing timely access to patients, and redesigning the delivery system to enhance clinical practices for healthcare staff (Siminerio et al., 2006). Implementing these elements ensures effective care for older adults, improving satisfaction. These components are designed to organize decision support, connect healthcare systems with community resources, deliver self-management support services, and manage patient-centered clinical information systems. Siminerio et al. (2006) found that applying these elements to diabetic patients resulted in practical diabetes self-management training for staff, recommending a standardized approach to training and improved collaboration in finance, administration, and information systems.

Current chronic disease care models focus on continuous care, but some gaps may negatively impact patients' experiences. A robust chronic care management plan can significantly enhance patients' quality of life, reduce concerns or anxiety, and increase satisfaction. Applying CCM principles to elderly chronic care management can improve workflow and overall care (Former, 2011). Coye (2016) suggested that Remote Patient Management (RPM) is a promising technology that supports self-management for chronic diseases, allows non-clinical caregivers to contribute, and can significantly improve patient quality of life. However, some patients may hesitate to use RPM due to the need for experience with remote medical technologies and the lack of guidance.

Chronic diseases pose a severe threat to elderly individuals' quality of life and significantly impact their families and the healthcare system. Developing effective chronic care management is challenging, especially when combined with financial issues that can exacerbate patients' health conditions due to stress from job loss or the high cost of treatment. Efforts have been made to address payment barriers and highlight how financial challenges can risk patients' overall health (Tsiachristas et al., 2011).

The CCM program is provided by a multidisciplinary team of specialists, including doctors, clinical nurse specialists, midwives, physician assistants, and nurse practitioners in hospitals and home nursing. Healthcare workers must integrate structured health information recording, including medication, allergy, and demographic data, using EHRs. This service is essential

for patients with complicated illnesses, improving their health outcomes and quality of life through effective communication and condition management (Spoorenberg et al., 2015). Healthcare workers must participate in educational development programs that enhance self-efficacy and clinical outcomes for older patients with chronic diseases. You and Beresford (2010) emphasized the importance of healthcare workers engaging in collaborative learning experiences and residency programs to develop the skills needed to implement CCM effectively.

CCM has been shown to reduce depressive symptoms, improve health-related quality of life, and increase patient satisfaction. Spoorenberg et al. (2015) stated that CCM provides a service for patients with complicated illnesses, facilitating communication to coordinate and improve health outcomes and quality of life. It is also evident that elderly patients need support to address their social needs and cope with aging and the loss of physical activities. However, one limitation is the patients' ability to communicate their experiences effectively. Additionally, CCM can enhance patients' psychological outcomes by providing a framework for patient-centered medical homes (Woltmann et al., 2012). The implementation of CCM in healthcare facilities includes a triple-aim plan to improve individual and population health and reduce healthcare costs, which ultimately eases patients' satisfaction levels (Woltmann et al., 2012).

In conclusion, elderly patients deserve complete care considering their age and level of education, which some studies have overlooked, affecting their ability to understand and accept the care provided. The educational development of community nurses has prepared them to provide effective encounters that improve self-efficacy and clinical outcomes for older adults with chronic conditions. Nurses must implement CCM elements to benefit the elderly population, improving health satisfaction among elderly patients with chronic health conditions. This paper aims to identify how CCM leads to satisfaction in elderly patients with chronic conditions and the roles of healthcare providers in CCM.

Research Method

Study Design

A scoping review was conducted following the framework developed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005). This approach was chosen because the subject area is complex and has not been comprehensively reviewed. In a scoping review, articles are included based on their relevance to the research questions rather than their methodological quality. The review process followed five phases, similar to those in systematic reviews, as

outlined below.

Identifying the Research Question

Based on an initial review, the research team formulated the following questions:

- How does the Chronic Care Model (CCM) contribute to satisfaction among elderly patients with chronic conditions?
- What role do healthcare providers play in achieving this satisfaction?

Identifying Relevant Studies

The search strategy focused on three key concepts: 'chronic disease,' 'Chronic Care Model,' 'satisfaction,' 'experience,' 'nurse,' and 'elderly.' The review included searches in databases such as PubMed, MEDLINE, ScienceDirect, PMC, Health Affairs, AJP, Wiley Online Library, ResearchGate, SpringerLink, CINAHL, Cochrane, and PsycINFO. Additionally, reference lists of relevant articles were reviewed to identify further studies.

Study Selection

Three reviewers independently conducted the search and selected studies in three phases: title screening, abstract screening, and full-text screening. Any discrepancies or uncertainties were resolved through consensus and expert opinion. Only studies written in English that focused on the CCM for the elderly population discussed the role of community health nurses and investigated patient outcomes, including satisfaction and experience, were included. Studies published in other languages or those not discussing CCM and patient outcomes among the elderly were excluded. A broad range of studies, including discussion papers, literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and program evaluations, were included without applying strict methodological criteria.

Charting the Data

The reviewers used a spreadsheet (Excel) to record and summarise information from each study. This spreadsheet included publication year, study type, title, purpose, design, population and sample, clinical system, key findings, and conclusions (see Appendix 1 for the Excel sheet). Each reviewer independently charted the data and discussed the results with an expert.

Collecting, Summarizing, and Reporting the Results

After an initial reading and preliminary content analysis, three key themes were identified: the Chronic Care Models, their principles and programs, and their implementation; the role of nurses in implementing and achieving the outcomes of the Chronic Care Models; and patient outcomes, including satisfaction and experience. A deductive reasoning approach was used

for the directed content analysis to examine the extent of these preliminary themes. The three reviewers independently extracted the information and discussed the findings until they reached a consensus. An expert was consulted in cases where questions remained unresolved or no consensus was reached.

Results

As illustrated in Figure 1, the initial number of articles identified was 2,544. After screening, which included reading titles, abstracts, and full texts and removing duplicates, 25 articles met the specified criteria. Among these, 19 articles were published in 2012, with the remaining published in 2006. The types of articles were categorized as follows: literature reviews (n=10), original papers (n=5), systematic reviews (n=4), systematic reviews and meta-analyses (n=3), study protocols (n=2), and one discussion paper (n=1). The original studies employed various research designs, including pre and post-test designs (n=2), qualitative designs (n=2), and mixed-method designs (n=1), focusing on evaluating chronic care.

Most of the studies and their citations centered on adopting chronic care models in developed countries. Specifically, three studies were conducted in the Netherlands (Muntinga et al., 2012; Spoorenberg et al., 2015; Walters et al., 2012), and one focused on the USA (Enderlin et al., 2013).

Chronic Care Models, Principles, and Programs and Their Implementation

The selected articles explored various approaches to implementing chronic care models and programs. These approaches included critical components of chronic care models, such as community and health systems, self-management support, decision support, clinical information systems, and delivery system design, utilized in the included studies. Many articles discussed all the primary components of the Chronic Care Model (CCM) (Adams et al., 2007; Coleman et al., 2009; Enderlin et al., 2013; Fromer, 2011; Siminerio et al., 2019; Stellefson et al., 2013; Walters et al., 2012; Wodchis et al. 2018).

Figure 1: Study Selection Process models and programs.

Seven studies incorporated one or more components (Cooper & McCarter, 2014; Coye et

al., 2009; Drouin et al., 2015; Sanna & Reuben, 2013; Spoorenberg et al. 2015; Tsiachristas et al. 2011). For instance, Spoorenberg et al. (2015) examined the opinions and experiences of older adults in the community regarding integrated care and support and its ability to meet their health and social needs. Cooper and McCarter (2014) focused on enhancing self-management efficacy within health systems. Sanna and Reuben (2013) and Drouin et al. (2015) discussed care delivery and the health system. Coye et al. (2009) emphasized the role of

clinical information systems in improving patient management, while Tsiachristas et al. (2011) addressed policy development to overcome financial barriers, focusing on clinical information systems and health delivery systems. Gee et al. (2015) explored the role of clinical information systems (e-health) in improving care.

Six studies specifically addressed the implementation of CCM for individuals with chronic diseases like diabetes and COPD. Desmedt et al. (2016) evaluated the costs and potential financial benefits of integrated care models for patients with chronic conditions such as type 2 diabetes mellitus, schizophrenia, and multiple sclerosis. Fromer (2011) and Adams et al. (2007) discussed the implementation of CCM for COPD patients. Siminerio et al. (2009) applied components of the CCM to implement and sustain a diabetes self-management training program. Stellefson et al. (2013) discussed how CCM had been applied in U.S. primary care settings to provide care for people with diabetes. Tempel et al. (2017) employed a mixed-method approach to analyze patients' needs for individualized chronic care models. Woltmann (2012) measured the effectiveness of collaborative chronic care models for mental health conditions across various healthcare settings.

Three studies explored the barriers and limitations of CCM implementation. Kadu and Stolee (2015) reviewed the facilitators and barriers to implementing CCM in primary care. Yeoh et al. (2018) examined the benefits and limitations of CCM implementation in primary care programs. Tsiachristas et al. (2011) discussed policy development to address financial barriers, focusing on clinical information and health delivery

systems.

Two articles discussed how CCM supports successful care transitions. Enderlin et al. (2013) highlighted the systematic approach and individualized care in CCM that meet patient and family health literacy, cognitive, and sensory needs. Sendall et al. (2012) explored how CCM components aid in the transition between different types of healthcare services for older adults with multiple chronic diseases.

Three articles focused on the role of clinical information systems in chronic care models. Coye et al. (2009) emphasized improving patient management through clinical information systems. Tsiachristas et al. (2011) discussed policy development to overcome financial barriers, focusing on clinical information and health delivery systems. Gee et al. (2015) examined the role of clinical information systems (e-health) in enhancing care.

Two proposals were developed regarding the implementation of chronic care models. Muntinga et al. (2012) and Frank et al. (2019) developed study protocols for implementing care management and chronic care models. One article explored international collaboration in implementing integrated care for older adults with complex health needs (Wodchis et al., 2018).

Role of Health Providers in Implementation and Achieving the Outcomes of CCM

Many of the included studies examined the role of healthcare providers as a team in implementing CCM and improving patient outcomes. Several studies highlighted their role as clinical resources for model implementation (Coye et al., 2009; Drouin et al., 2015; Siminerio et al., 2019). Others focused on their roles in patient and family education (Cooper & McCarter, 2014; Gee et al., 2015; Timpel et al., 2017), community education about managing chronic conditions, promoting healthy choices, patient care delivery, wellness projects, infection control, emergency safety methods, and nutrition (Chafee et al., 2015; Cooper & McCarter, 2014; Sanna & Reuben 2013).

Many articles discussed the role of healthcare providers in coordinating patient care (Busetto,

Luijkx, and Vrijhoef 2016; Coye, Haselkorn, and DeMello 2009; Drouin et al. 2015; Fromer 2011; Gill et al. 2020; Siminerio et al. 2019), patient follow-up and transition (Fromer 2011; Muntinga et al. 2012; Sanna and Reuben 2013; Sendall et al. 2017), promoting healthy lifestyles (Smith and Ryckman 2015), disease prevention (Adams et al. 2007; Masaki et al. 2007; Stellefson, Dipnarine, and Stopka 2013), providing direct patient care (Gee et al. 2015; Walters et al. 2012), improving self-care abilities (Cooper and McCarter 2014; Fromer 2011; Gee et al. 2015; Sanna and Reuben 2013), enhancing treatment compliance (Yeoh et al. 2018), leading health and wellness programs (Cooper and McCarter 2014; Nahm et al. 2019; Wodchis et al. 2018), and offering individualized, patient-centered care (Fromer 2011; Kendall et al. 2015; Spoorenberg et al. 2015; Stellefson, Dipnarine, and Stopka 2013; Walters et al. 2012).

Additionally, other articles discussed the roles of healthcare providers as information-sharing agents between healthcare professionals and patients, data generation and analysis, conducting research and auditing provided care (Coye et al., 2009; Fromer, 2011; Gill et al., 2020; Muntinga et al. 2012; Sendall et al. 2017; Tsiachristas et al. 2011; Woltmann et al. 2012), as well as advancements in communication and technology (Andrès et al., 2019; Coye et al., 2009; Gee et al., 2015; Nahm et al. 2019; Tsiachristas et al. 2011; Walters et al. 2012).

Several studies highlighted the role of healthcare providers in redesigning systems (Gee et al., 2015; Kadu & Stolee, 2015; Al Qadire, 2014; Tsiachristas et al., 2011) and redefining services and cost-saving measures (Desmedt et al., 2016; Marcelli et al. 2017, n.d.; Pem & Jeewon, 2015).

Patient Outcomes

The included articles demonstrated the impact of chronic care models and programs on achieving patient clinical outcomes, improving the quality of care, and enhancing patient experience, leading to increased patient satisfaction.

Clinical Outcomes

Numerous articles highlighted the role of CCM in achieving clinical outcomes. Siminerio et al.

(2009) noted that chronic care models contributed to reducing hemoglobin A1C levels ($P < .0001$) and increasing the proportion of patients receiving DSMT through delivery in primary care (26.4% suburban; 19.8% urban) versus hospital-based practices (8.3%; $P < .0001$). Cooper (2013) demonstrated how implementing chronic care models helped control patient blood pressure and weight. Drouin et al. (2015) emphasized the role of CCM in improving outcomes for diabetes patients, including blood pressure, HbA1c levels, LDL cholesterol levels, and nutritional status. Former (2011) illustrated how CCM improved risk awareness, spirometric diagnosis, guideline-based treatment and rehabilitation, and self-management support, all contributing to better patient outcomes for COPD patients. Coleman et al. (2009) showed that redesigning care using CCM improved patient care and health outcomes.

Hopman et al. (2016) suggested that providing comprehensive care through chronic care models could result in fewer depressive symptoms and better functioning in multimorbid or frail patients. Woltmann (2012) reported that CCM could improve mental and physical outcomes for individuals with mental disorders across diverse care settings, offering a robust clinical and policy framework for care integration.

Improving Quality of Care

Several studies demonstrated the role of CCM implementation in enhancing the quality of care. Drouin et al. (2015) discussed the positive effects of CCM on providers' and patients' perspectives of care quality and patient-related care processes. Tsiachristas et al. (2011) highlighted the link between quality and cost in CCM implementation. Stellefson, Dipnarine, and Stopka (2013) noted that CCM approaches effectively managed diabetes in U.S. primary care settings, leading to system-level reorganizations that improved care coordination and patient outcomes. Kadu and Stolee (2015) emphasized the importance of assessing organizational capacity and improving patient care quality during CCM implementation. Hopman et al. (2016) mentioned that comprehensive care might improve health-related quality of life.

Improving Patient Journey, Experience, and

Satisfaction

Numerous articles explored the impact of CCM on patient experience. Spooenberg et al. (2015) demonstrated that CCM implementation increased patients' ability to maintain control, even when dependent on others, and improved their safety and security. Enderlin et al. (2013) discussed how CCM improved individualized care to meet patient and family health literacy and cognitive and sensory needs. Cooper (2013) highlighted increased patient participation and self-efficacy with CCM implementation. Sanna and Reuben (2013) noted that CCM standardized and guided care provision. Drouin et al. (2015) indicated that CCM reduced emergency department visits and readmission rates, thus improving patient journeys.

Former (2011) showed how CCM standardized care processes, enhancing visit planning, care workflows, care coordination, and patient empowerment. Coye et al. (2009) mentioned that CCM supported patient self-management, shifted responsibilities to non-clinical providers, and reduced emergency department and hospital service use. Tsiachristas et al. (2011) noted that proper policy development facilitated communication between caregivers, expanded the scope of specialized care, and supported through economic evaluations. Wodchis et al. (2018) suggested that community-based primary health care (CBPHC) associated with CCM offered more equitable access to services, better population-level outcomes, and lower system-level costs. Adams et al. (2007) mentioned that patients with COPD who received interventions with two or more CCM components had lower hospitalization rates, fewer emergency/unscheduled visits, and shorter stay lengths than control groups.

Desmedt et al. (2016) reported that integrated care models for patients with chronic diseases had predominantly positive economic impacts, potentially enhancing patient satisfaction by reducing care costs. Gee et al. (2015) discussed the role of electronic CCM in supporting self-management for people with chronic conditions, suggesting further research and testing of the eCCM. Yeoh et al. (2018) identified the benefits of CCM implementation, including reduced health service utilization and lower risks of heart failure

and cardiovascular diseases. Hopman et al. (2016) mentioned that comprehensive care might increase patient satisfaction. Marcelli (2017) indicated that CCM is a practical starting point for better resource management, enhancing care coordination and accessibility. Sendall et al. (2017) found that CCM implementation in a health service improved the transition between hospital and ambulatory settings, health outcomes, and patient experiences. Tempel et al. (2017) concluded that chronic care management improved financial support, case management, consideration of individual patient needs, promotion of active patient involvement, and social care.

Discussion

The study addressed the specified questions, namely, "How does the Chronic Care Model (CCM) lead to satisfaction among elderly individuals with chronic conditions?" and "What is the role of nurses in achieving such satisfaction?" by analyzing 25 articles that utilized various designs and approaches across different settings and regions.

The study reviewed and described chronic care models and their implementation in diverse settings. It then identified nurses' roles in this implementation process and discussed the outcomes of these implementations. A content analysis approach was employed to deepen the understanding of the study variables.

The review of chronic care models, principles, and programs within the included articles provides a comprehensive understanding of how these models contribute to patient outcomes and satisfaction. The articles examined various approaches to the implementation of chronic care models and programs, utilizing all or some of the critical components of the models (Adams et al., 2007; Coleman et al., 2009; Cooper & McCarter 2014; Coye, Haselkorn, and DeMello 2009; Drouin et al. 2015; Enderlin et al. 2013; Fromer 2011; Sanna and Reuben 2013; Siminerio et al. 2019; Spooenberg et al. 2015; Stellefson, Dipnarine, and Stopka 2013; Tsiachristas et al. 2011; Walters et al. 2012; Wodchis et al. 2018). This helps clarify the role of each component in enhancing patient outcomes.

Additionally, the articles discussed the implementation of CCM in general and specific chronic diseases such as diabetes and COPD, which improves our understanding of the impact of chronic care models across different

settings in enhancing patient outcomes. Consequently, the findings of this review could be generalized to various healthcare settings, as many articles discussed the barriers and limitations of CCM implementation (Kadu and Stolee, 2015; Tsiachristas et al., 2011; Yeoh et al., 2018), as well as the processes and factors involved in implementation, such as care transitions (Enderlin et al., 2013; Sendall et al. 2017) and clinical information systems (Coye et al., 2009; Gee et al. 2015; Tsiachristas et al. 2011). Moreover, the included studies provided evidence-based proposals and plans for implementing chronic care models, offering current and updated perspectives on implementation (Frank et al., 2019; Muntinga et al., 2012).

The majority of the included studies explored the roles of nurses as part of the team in implementing CCM and improving patient outcomes, highlighting the critical role nurses, as primary healthcare providers, play in achieving these outcomes (Coye et al., 2009; Drouin et al., 2015; Siminerio et al., 2019). Nurses' roles in the model's implementation were broad, encompassing direct care provision, patient and community health education, care coordination and navigation, leading and managing health and wellness programs, providing individualized and patient-centered care, and acting as information-sharing agents. Understanding these roles can help in anticipating and interpreting patient outcomes.

Patient outcomes were categorized into three main areas: clinical outcomes, quality of care, and patient journey, experience, and satisfaction. Clinical outcomes, quality of care, a well-structured patient journey, and a positive experience were all significantly associated with patient satisfaction (Fromer, 2011). Given this, the ultimate impact of these models on elderly satisfaction was assessed based on the implementation of the models in various settings. Therefore, our findings on improving patient outcomes and satisfaction could be generalized across different settings. Generally, patient satisfaction can be achieved by delivering appropriate, evidence-based, patient-centered care, ensuring proper care coordination and management, engaging and empowering patients, redesigning workplaces, providing cost-effective treatment, improving patient accessibility, and enhancing patient self-management.

For these reasons, it is recommended that healthcare leaders educate healthcare providers, including nurses, about CCM and its implementation, assess organizational capacity to adopt chronic care models, develop policies guiding CCM implementation, and utilize proper auditing and follow-up systems.

Conclusion

This review confirmed the role of adopting CCM in enhancing patient experience and satisfaction in chronic care settings. It also validated the positive roles of nurses in achieving desired patient outcomes, including clinical outcomes, high-quality care, and patient satisfaction. However, several limitations were encountered during this review, including time constraints, a lack of updated original articles, and the definition of nurses' roles as part of a team in the included studies. Further research is recommended to explore the adoption of CCM and its impact in developing countries.

References

- Adams, Sandra G. et al. 2007. "Systematic Review of the Chronic Care Model in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Prevention and Management." *Archives of Internal Medicine* 167(6): 551–61. <https://jamanetwork.com/> (October 26, 2020).
- Al Qadire, Mohammad. 2014. "Jordanian Cancer Patients' Information Needs and Information-Seeking Behaviour: A Descriptive Study." *European Journal of Oncology Nursing*.
- Al Qadire, Mohammad. 2014. "Jordanian Cancer Patients' Information Needs and Information-Seeking Behaviour: A Descriptive Study." *European Journal of Oncology Nursing*.
- Andrès, Emmanuel, Samy Talha, Mohamed Hajjam, and Amir Hajjam El Hassani. 2019. "Telemedicine for Chronic Heart Failure: An Update." In *Topics in Heart Failure Management*, IntechOpen.
- Andrès, Emmanuel, Samy Talha, Mohamed Hajjam, and Amir Hajjam El Hassani. 2019. "Telemedicine for Chronic Heart Failure: An Update." In *Topics in Heart Failure Management*, IntechOpen.
- Arksey, H., & O'Malley, L. (2005). Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *International journal of social research methodology*, 8(1), 19-32.
- Adams, Sandra G. et al. 2007. "Systematic Review of the Chronic Care Model in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Prevention and Management." *Archives of Internal Medicine* 167(6): 551–61. <https://jamanetwork.com/> (October 26, 2020).
- Arksey, H., & O'Malley, L. (2005). Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *International journal of social research methodology*, 8(1), 19-32.
- Busetto, Loraine, Katrien Luijkx, and Hubertus Johannes Maria Vrijhoef. 2016. "Development of the COMIC Model for the Comprehensive Evaluation of Integrated Care Interventions." *International Journal of Care Coordination* 19(1–2): 47–58. <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2053434516661700> (July 3, 2020).
- Busetto, Loraine, Katrien Luijkx, and Hubertus Johannes Maria Vrijhoef. 2016. "Development of the COMIC Model for the Comprehensive Evaluation of Integrated Care Interventions." *International Journal of Care Coordination* 19(1–2): 47–58. <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2053434516661700> (July 3, 2020).
- Chafee, A. et al. 2015. "Providing a Safety Net for Bone Marrow Transplant (BMT) Survivors: Nurses and Telephone Triage." *Biology of Blood and Marrow Transplantation* 21(2 SUPPL. 1): S383.

- Chafee, A. et al. 2015. "Providing a Safety Net for Bone Marrow Transplant (BMT) Survivors: Nurses and Telephone Triage." *Biology of Blood and Marrow Transplantation* 21(2 SUPPL. 1): S383.
- Coleman, K., Austin, B., Brach, C. and Wanger, E. (2009). Evidence On The Chronic Care Model In The New Millennium. *Health Affairs*, 28(1), doi: 10.1377/hlthaff.28.1.75. <https://www.healthaffairs.org/doi/full/10.1377/hlthaff.28.1.75>
- Coleman, K., Austin, B., Brach, C. and Wanger, E. (2009). Evidence On The Chronic Care Model In The New Millennium. *Health Affairs*, 28(1), doi: 10.1377/hlthaff.28.1.75. <https://www.healthaffairs.org/doi/full/10.1377/hlthaff.28.1.75>
- Coleman, Katie, Brian T. Austin, Cindy Brach, and Edward H. Wagner. 2009. "Evidence on the Chronic Care Model in the New Millennium." *Health Affairs* 28(1): 75–85.
- Coleman, Katie, Brian T. Austin, Cindy Brach, and Edward H. Wagner. 2009. "Evidence on the Chronic Care Model in the New Millennium." *Health Affairs* 28(1): 75–85.
- Cooper, J., and McCarter. K. (2013). The Development of a Community and Home-Based Chronic Care Management Program for Older Adults. *Public Health Nursing*, 31(1), doi: 10.1111/phn.12049. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/phn.12049>
- Cooper, J., and McCarter. K. (2013). The Development of a Community and Home-Based Chronic Care Management Program for Older Adults. *Public Health Nursing*, 31(1), doi: 10.1111/phn.12049. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/phn.12049>
- Cooper, Jennifer, and Kathryn A. McCarter. 2014. "The Development of a Community and Home-Based Chronic Care Management Program for Older Adults." *Public Health Nursing* 31(1): 36–43. <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/phn.12049> (October 26, 2020).
- Cooper, Jennifer, and Kathryn A. McCarter. 2014. "The Development of a Community and Home-Based Chronic Care Management Program for Older Adults." *Public Health Nursing* 31(1): 36–43. <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/phn.12049> (October 26, 2020).
- Coye, M., Haselkorn, A. and DeMello, S. (2009). Remote Patient Management: Technology-Enabled Innovation And Evolving Business Models For Chronic Disease Care. *Health Affairs*, 28(1), 126-135. doi: 10.1377/hlthaff.28.1.126. <https://www.healthaffairs.org/doi/full/10.1377/hlthaff.28.1.126>
- Coye, M., Haselkorn, A. and DeMello, S. (2009). Remote Patient Management: Technology-Enabled Innovation And Evolving Business Models For Chronic Disease Care. *Health Affairs*, 28(1), 126-135. doi: 10.1377/hlthaff.28.1.126. <https://www.healthaffairs.org/doi/full/10.1377/hlthaff.28.1.126>
- Coye, Molly Joel, Ateret Haselkorn, and Steven DeMello. 2009. "Remote Patient Management: Technology-Enabled Innovation and Evolving Business Models for Chronic Disease Care." *Health Affairs* 28(1): 126–35.
- Coye, Molly Joel, Ateret Haselkorn, and Steven DeMello. 2009. "Remote Patient Management: Technology-Enabled Innovation and Evolving Business Models for Chronic Disease Care." *Health Affairs* 28(1): 126–35.
- Desmedt, Melissa et al. 2016. "Economic Impact of Integrated Care Models for Patients with Chronic Diseases: A Systematic Review." *Value in Health* 19(6): 892–902.
- Desmedt, Melissa et al. 2016. "Economic Impact of Integrated Care Models for Patients with Chronic Diseases: A Systematic Review." *Value in Health* 19(6): 892–902.
- Drouin, H, Walker, J., McNeil, Elliott, J. and Stolee, P. (2015). Measured outcomes of chronic care programs for older adults: a systematic review. *BMC Geriatric*, 15(139), 1-9. DOI 10.1186/s12877-015-0136-7. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12877-015-0136-7>
- Drouin, H, Walker, J., McNeil, Elliott, J., and Stolee, P. (2015). Measured outcomes of chronic care programs for older adults: a systematic review. *BMC Geriatric*, 15(139), 1-9. DOI 10.1186/s12877-015-0136-7. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12877-015-0136-7>
- Drouin, Heather et al. 2015. "Measured Outcomes of Chronic Care Programs for Older Adults: A Systematic Review Health Services Research." *BMC Geriatrics* 15(1): 1–9. <https://link.springer.com/articles/10.1186/s12877-015-0136-7> (October 26, 2020).
- Drouin, Heather et al. 2015. "Measured Outcomes of Chronic Care Programs for Older Adults: A Systematic Review Health Services Research." *BMC Geriatrics* 15(1): 1–9. <https://link.springer.com/articles/10.1186/s12877-015-0136-7> (October 26, 2020).
- Enderlin, Carol A. et al. 2013. "Review of Current Conceptual Models and Frameworks to Guide Transitions of Care in Older Adults." *Geriatric Nursing* 34(1): 47–52.
- Enderlin, Carol A. et al. 2013. "Review of Current Conceptual Models and Frameworks to Guide Transitions of Care in Older Adults." *Geriatric Nursing* 34(1): 47–52.
- Endrline, C., McLeskey, N., and Ennenf, J. (2013). Review current conceptual models and frameworks to guide care transitions in older adults. *Geriatric Nursing*, 34(1), 47-52. doi: 10.1016/j.gerinurse.2012.08.003. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0197457212002789>
- Endrline, C., McLeskey, N., and Ennenf, J. (2013). Review of current conceptual models and frameworks to guide transitions of care in older adults. *Geriatric Nursing*, 34(1), 47-52. doi: 10.1016/j.gerinurse.2012.08.003. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0197457212002789>
- Former, L. (2011). Implementing chronic care for COPD: planned visits, care coordination, and patient empowerment for improved outcomes. *International Journal of Chronic Obstruction Pulmonary Disease*, 2011(6), 605-614. doi: 10.2147/COPD.S24692 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3232168/>
- Former, L. (2011). Implementing chronic care for COPD: planned visits, care coordination, and patient empowerment for improved outcomes. *International Journal of Chronic Obstruction Pulmonary Disease*, 2011(6), 605-614. doi 10.2147/COPD.S24692 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3232168/>
- Frank, Fabian, et al. 2019. "Local, Collaborative, Stepped and Personalised Care Management for Older People with Chronic Diseases (LoChro): Study Protocol of a Randomised Comparative Effectiveness Trial." *BMC Geriatrics* 19(1): 64. <https://bmgeriatr.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12877-019-1088-0> (October 26, 2020).

- Frank, Fabian, et al. 2019. "Local, Collaborative, Stepped and Personalised Care Management for Older People with Chronic Diseases (LoChro): Study Protocol of a Randomised Comparative Effectiveness Trial." *BMC Geriatrics* 19(1): 64. <https://bmgeriatr.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12877-019-1088-0> (October 26, 2020).
- Fromer, Len. 2011. "Implementing Chronic Care for COPD: Planned Visits, Care Coordination, and Patient Empowerment for Improved Outcomes." *International Journal of COPD* 6(1): 605–14. [/pmc/articles/PMC3232168/?report=abstract](https://pmc/articles/PMC3232168/?report=abstract) (October 26, 2020).
- Fromer, Len. 2011. "Implementing Chronic Care for COPD: Planned Visits, Care Coordination, and Patient Empowerment for Improved Outcomes." *International Journal of COPD* 6(1): 605–14. [/pmc/articles/PMC3232168/?report=abstract](https://pmc/articles/PMC3232168/?report=abstract) (October 26, 2020).
- Gee, Perry M. et al. 2015. "The EHealth Enhanced Chronic Care Model: A Theory Derivation Approach." *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 17(4): e86. <https://www.jmir.org/2015/4/e86/> (October 26, 2020).
- Gee, Perry M. et al. 2015. "The EHealth Enhanced Chronic Care Model: A Theory Derivation Approach." *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 17(4): e86. <https://www.jmir.org/2015/4/e86/> (October 26, 2020).
- Gill, Emily et al. 2020. "Technology-Facilitated Care Coordination in Rural Areas: What Is Needed?" *International Journal of Medical Informatics* 137: 104102.
- Gill, Emily et al. 2020. "Technology-Facilitated Care Coordination in Rural Areas: What Is Needed?" *International Journal of Medical Informatics* 137: 104102.
- Hopman, P., de Bruin, S, Forjaz, M., Rodriguez-Blazquez, C., Tonnara, G., Lemmensb G., Ondere, C., Bann, C. and Rijken, M. (2016). Effectiveness of comprehensive care programs for patients with multiple chronic conditions or frailty: A systematic literature review. *Health Policy*, 120(7), 818-832. doi: 10.1016/j.healthpol.2016.04.002. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0168851016300793>
- Hopman, P., de Bruin, S, Forjaz, M., Rodriguez-Blazquez, C., Tonnara, G., Lemmensb G., Ondere, C., Bann, C. and Rijken, M. (2016). Effectiveness of comprehensive care programs for patients with multiple chronic conditions or frailty: A systematic literature review. *Health Policy*, 120(7), 818-832. doi: 10.1016/j.healthpol.2016.04.002. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0168851016300793>
- Hopman, Petra et al. 2016. "Effectiveness of Comprehensive Care Programs for Patients with Multiple Chronic Conditions or Frailty: A Systematic Literature Review." *Health Policy* 120(7): 818–32.
- Hopman, Petra et al. 2016. "Effectiveness of Comprehensive Care Programs for Patients with Multiple Chronic Conditions or Frailty: A Systematic Literature Review." *Health Policy* 120(7): 818–32.
- Kadu, Mudathira K., and Paul Stolee. 2015. "Facilitators and Barriers of Implementing the Chronic Care Model in Primary Care: A Systematic Review." *BMC Family Practice* 16(1): 1–14. <https://link.springer.com/articles/10.1186/s12875-014-0219-0> (October 26, 2020).
- Kadu, Mudathira K., and Paul Stolee. 2015. "Facilitators and Barriers of Implementing the Chronic Care Model in Primary Care: A Systematic Review." *BMC Family Practice* 16(1): 1–14. <https://link.springer.com/articles/10.1186/s12875-014-0219-0> (October 26, 2020).
- Kendall, Marilyn, et al. 2015. "Different Experiences and Goals in Different Advanced Diseases: Comparing Serial Interviews With Patients With Cancer, Organ Failure, or Frailty and Their Family and Professional Carers." *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management* 50(2): 216–24. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0885392415015130> (December 27, 2018).
- Kendall, Marilyn, et al. 2015. "Different Experiences and Goals in Different Advanced Diseases: Comparing Serial Interviews With Patients With Cancer, Organ Failure, or Frailty and Their Family and Professional Carers." *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management* 50(2): 216–24. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0885392415015130> (December 27, 2018).
- Marcelli, Stefano et al. 2017. "Chronic Care Model and Cost Reduction in Initial Health: A New Approach for Satisfaction and Improvement of Chronicity." *Geriatric Care*.
- Marcelli, Stefano et al. 2017. "Chronic Care Model and Cost Reduction in Initial Health: A New Approach for Satisfaction and Improvement of Chronicity." *Geriatric Care*.
- Masaki, Fujioka et al. 2007. "Evaluation of Pressure Ulcers in 202 Patients with Cancer -Do Patients with Cancer Tend to Develop Pressure Ulcers?" *Wounds* 19(1). <http://www.woundsresearch.com/article/6706>.
- Masaki, Fujioka et al. 2007. "Evaluation of Pressure Ulcers in 202 Patients with Cancer -Do Patients with Cancer Tend to Develop Pressure Ulcers?" *Wounds* 19(1). <http://www.woundsresearch.com/article/6706>.
- Muntinga, Maaik E. et al. 2012. "Implementing the Chronic Care Model for Frail Older Adults in the Netherlands: Study Protocol of ACT (Frail Older Adults: Care in Transition)." *BMC Geriatrics* 12(1): 1–10. <https://link.springer.com/articles/10.1186/1471-2318-12-19> (October 26, 2020).
- Muntinga, Maaik E. et al. 2012. "Implementing the Chronic Care Model for Frail Older Adults in the Netherlands: Study Protocol of ACT (Frail Older Adults: Care in Transition)." *BMC Geriatrics* 12(1): 1–10. <https://link.springer.com/articles/10.1186/1471-2318-12-19> (October 26, 2020).
- Nahm, Eun-Shim et al. 2019. "The Effects of a Theory-Based Patient Portal e-Learning Program for Older Adults with Chronic Illnesses." *Telemedicine and e-Health* 25(10): 940–51. <https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/tmj.2018.0184> (April 9, 2020).
- Nahm, Eun-Shim et al. 2019. "The Effects of a Theory-Based Patient Portal e-Learning Program for Older Adults with Chronic Illnesses." *Telemedicine and e-Health* 25(10): 940–51. <https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/tmj.2018.0184> (April 9, 2020).
- Pem, D. and, and R. Jeewon. 2015. "Fruit and Vegetable Intake: Benefits and Progress of Nutrition Education Interventions- Narrative Review Article." *Iranian journal of public health*.
- Pem, D. and, and R. Jeewon. 2015. "Fruit and Vegetable Intake: Benefits and Progress of Nutrition Education Interventions- Narrative Review Article." *Iranian journal of public health*.

- Sanna, M. and Reuben, M. (2013). Transforming Chronic Care for Older Adults: Guided Care and the Elusive Triple Aim. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 28(5), 603–604. doi: 10.1007/s11606-013-2358-8. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11606-013-2358-8>
- Sanna, M. and Reuben, M. (2013). Transforming Chronic Care for Older Adults: Guided Care and the Elusive Triple Aim. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 28(5), 603–604. doi: 10.1007/s11606-013-2358-8. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11606-013-2358-8>
- Sanna, Maija B, and David B Reuben. 2013. “Transforming Chronic Care for Older Adults: Guided Care and the Elusive Triple Aim.” *J Gen Intern Med* 28(5): 603–7. <http://www.cbo.gov/sites/default/files/2013/10/20131026-Transforming-Chronic-Care-for-Older-Adults-Guided-Care-and-the-Elusive-Triple-Aim.pdf> (October 26, 2020).
- Sanna, Maija B, and David B Reuben. 2013. “Transforming Chronic Care for Older Adults: Guided Care and the Elusive Triple Aim.” *J Gen Intern Med* 28(5): 603–7. <http://www.cbo.gov/sites/default/files/2013/10/20131026-Transforming-Chronic-Care-for-Older-Adults-Guided-Care-and-the-Elusive-Triple-Aim.pdf> (October 26, 2020).
- Sendall, Marguerite, Laura McCosker, Kristie Crossley, and Ann Bonner. 2017. “A Structured Review of Chronic Care Model Components Supporting Transition between Healthcare Service Delivery Types for Older People with Multiple Chronic Diseases.” *Health Information Management Journal* 46(2): 58–68. <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1833358316681687> (October 26, 2020).
- Sendall, Marguerite, Laura McCosker, Kristie Crossley, and Ann Bonner. 2017. “A Structured Review of Chronic Care Model Components Supporting Transition between Healthcare Service Delivery Types for Older People with Multiple Chronic Diseases.” *Health Information Management Journal* 46(2): 58–68. <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1833358316681687> (October 26, 2020).
- Siminerio, Linda, Gretchen Piatt, Kris Ruppert, and Melissa I Saul. 2019. “Deploying the Chronic Care Model to Implement and Sustain Diabetes Self-Management Training Programs Prescription Medication Use and Cognitive Function View Project.” <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/7225565> (October 26, 2020).
- Siminerio, Linda, Gretchen Piatt, Kris Ruppert, and Melissa I Saul. 2019. “Deploying the Chronic Care Model to Implement and Sustain Diabetes Self-Management Training Programs Prescription Medication Use and Cognitive Function View Project.” <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/7225565> (October 26, 2020).
- Siminerio, S., Piatt, G., Emerson, S., Ruppert, K., Saul, M., Solano, F., Stewart, A., and Zgibor, J. (2006). Deploying the Chronic Care Model to Implement a Sustain Diabetes Self-management Training Programs. *Diabetes Education*, 32(2), 253-260. Doi: 10.1177/0145721706287156. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Gretchen_Piatt/publication/7225565_Deploying_the_Chronic_Care_Model_to_Implement_and_Sustain_Diabetes_Self-management_Training_Programs/links/00b7d51ded4196b7570000/Deploying-the-Chronic-Care-Model-to-Implement-and-Sustain-Diabetes-Self-management-Training-Programs.pdf
- Siminerio, S., Piatt, G., Emerson, S., Ruppert, K., Saul, M., Solano, F., Stewart, A., and Zgibor, J. (2006). Deploying the Chronic Care Model to Implement and Sustain Diabetes Self-management Training Programs. *Diabetes Education*, 32(2), 253-260. Doi: 10.1177/0145721706287156.
- Smith, Caitlin J., and Kelli K. Ryckman. 2015. “Epigenetic and Developmental Influences on the Risk of Obesity, Diabetes, and Metabolic Syndrome.” *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Therapy*.
- Smith, Caitlin J., and Kelli K. Ryckman. 2015. “Epigenetic and Developmental Influences on the Risk of Obesity, Diabetes, and Metabolic Syndrome.” *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Therapy*.
- Spoorenberg, S., Wynia, K., Fokkens, A., Slotman, K., Kremer, H. and Reijmen, R. (2015). Experiences of Community-Living Older Adults Receiving Integrated Care Based on the Chronic Care Model: A Qualitative Study. *PLoS One*, 10(10): e0137803. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0137803 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4619446/>
- Spoorenberg, S., Wynia, K., Fokkens, A., Slotman, K., Kremer, H. and Reijmen, R. (2015). Experiences of Community-Living Older Adults Receiving Integrated Care Based on the Chronic Care Model: A Qualitative Study. *PLoS One*, 10(10): e0137803. Doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0137803
- Spoorenberg, Sophie L. W. et al. 2015. “Experiences of Community-Living Older Adults Receiving Integrated Care Based on the Chronic Care Model: A Qualitative Study” ed. Fiona Harris. *PLOS ONE* 10(10): e0137803. <https://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0137803> (October 26, 2020).
- Spoorenberg, Sophie L. W. et al. 2015. “Experiences of Community-Living Older Adults Receiving Integrated Care Based on the Chronic Care Model: A Qualitative Study” ed. Fiona Harris. *PLOS ONE* 10(10): e0137803. <https://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0137803> (October 26, 2020).
- Stellefson, M., Dipnarine, K. and Stopka, C. (2013). The Chronic Care Model and Diabetes Management in US Primary Care Settings: A Systematic Review. *Preview Chronic Disease*, 10(26), 1-10. doi: 10.5888/pcd10.120180. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3604796/>
- Stellefson, M., Dipnarine, K. and Stopka, C. (2013). The Chronic Care Model and Diabetes Management in US Primary Care Settings: A Systematic Review. *Preview Chronic Disease*, 10(26), 1-10. doi: 10.5888/pcd10.120180.
- Stellefson, Michael, Krishna Dipnarine, and Christine Stopka. 2013. “The Chronic Care Model and Diabetes Management in US Primary Care Settings: A Systematic Review.” *Preventing Chronic Disease* 10(2). </pmc/articles/PMC3604796/?report=abstract> (October 26, 2020).
- Stellefson, Michael, Krishna Dipnarine, and Christine Stopka. 2013. “The Chronic Care Model and Diabetes Management in US Primary Care Settings: A Systematic Review.” *Preventing Chronic Disease* 10(2). </pmc/articles/PMC3604796/?report=abstract> (October 26, 2020).
- Timpel, P. et al. 2017. “Individualising Chronic Care Management by Analysing Patients’ Needs – A Mixed Method Approach.” *International Journal of Integrated Care* 17(6). </pmc/articles/PMC5854149/?report=abstract> (October 26, 2020).
- Timpel, P. et al. 2017. “Individualising Chronic Care Management by Analysing Patients’ Needs – A Mixed Method Approach.” *International Journal of Integrated Care* 17(6). </pmc/articles/PMC5854149/?report=abstract> (October 26, 2020).
- Tsiachristas, A. Hipple-Walters, B, Lemmens, K., Niboer, A., Ruttenvan, M. (2011). Towards integrated care for chronic

- conditions: Dutch policy developments to overcome the (financial) barriers. *Health Policy*, 101(2), 122-132. doi: 10.1016/j.healthpol.2010.10.013. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0168851010003076>
- Tsiachristas, A. Hipple-Walters, B. Lemmens, K., Niboer, A., Ruttenvan, M. (2011). Towards integrated care for chronic conditions: Dutch policy developments to overcome the (financial) barriers. *Health Policy*, 101(2), 122-132. doi: 10.1016/j.healthpol.2010.10.013.
- Tsiachristas, Apostolos et al. 2011. "Towards Integrated Care for Chronic Conditions: Dutch Policy Developments to Overcome the (Financial) Barriers." *Health Policy* 101(2): 122–32.
- Tsiachristas, Apostolos et al. 2011. "Towards Integrated Care for Chronic Conditions: Dutch Policy Developments to Overcome the (Financial) Barriers." *Health Policy* 101(2): 122–32.
- Walters, B., Samantha, A., Nieboer A. and Bal, R. (2012). Disease management projects and the Chronic Care Model in action: baseline qualitative research. *BMC Health Services Research*, 12(114), doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-12-114 <https://bmchealthservres.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1472-6963-12-114>
- Walters, B., Samantha, A., Nieboer A. and Bal, R. (2012). Disease management projects and the Chronic Care Model in action: baseline qualitative research. *BMC Health Services Research*, 12(114), doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-12-114
- Walters, Bethany Hipple, Samantha A. Adams, Anna P. Nieboer, and Roland Bal. 2012. "Disease Management Projects and the Chronic Care Model in Action: Baseline Qualitative Research." *BMC Health Services Research* 12(1): 114. <https://bmchealthservres.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1472-6963-12-114> (October 26, 2020).
- Walters, Bethany Hipple, Samantha A. Adams, Anna P. Nieboer, and Roland Bal. 2012. "Disease Management Projects and the Chronic Care Model in Action: Baseline Qualitative Research." *BMC Health Services Research* 12(1): 114. <https://bmchealthservres.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1472-6963-12-114> (October 26, 2020).
- Wodchis, Walter P. et al. 2018. "A Research Program on Implementing Integrated Care for Older Adults with Complex Health Needs (ICOACH): An International Collaboration." *International Journal of Integrated Care* 18(2). [/pmc/articles/PMC6095069/?report=abstract](https://pmc/articles/PMC6095069/?report=abstract) (October 26, 2020).
- Wodchis, Walter P. et al. 2018. "A Research Program on Implementing Integrated Care for Older Adults with Complex Health Needs (COACH): An International Collaboration." *International Journal of Integrated Care* 18(2). [/pmc/articles/PMC6095069/?report=abstract](https://pmc/articles/PMC6095069/?report=abstract) (October 26, 2020).
- Woltmann, E., Grogan-Kaylor, A., Brian, P, Georges, H., Kilbourne, A. and Mark, B. (2012). Comparative Effectiveness of Collaborative Chronic Care Models for Mental Health Conditions Across Primary, Specialty, and Behavioral Health Care Settings: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. UK: Centre for Reviews and Dissemination. <https://ajp.psychiatryonline.org/doi/full/10.1176/appi.ajp.2012.11111616>
- Woltmann, Emily et al. 2012. "Comparative Effectiveness of Collaborative Chronic Care Models for Mental Health Conditions across Primary, Specialty, and Behavioral Health Care Settings: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis." *American Journal of Psychiatry* 169(8): 790–804. <https://ajp.psychiatryonline.org/doi/abs/10.1176/appi.ajp.2012.1111616> (October 26, 2020).
- Woltmann, Emily et al. 2012. "Comparative Effectiveness of Collaborative Chronic Care Models for Mental Health Conditions across Primary, Specialty, and Behavioral Health Care Settings: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis." *American Journal of Psychiatry* 169(8): 790–804. <https://ajp.psychiatryonline.org/doi/abs/10.1176/appi.ajp.2012.1111616> (October 26, 2020).
- Yeoh, E. K. et al. 2018. "Benefits and Limitations of Implementing Chronic Care Model (CCM) in Primary Care Programs: A Systematic Review." *International Journal of Cardiology* 258: 279–88.
- Yeoh, E. K. et al. 2018. "Benefits and Limitations of Implementing Chronic Care Model (CCM) in Primary Care Programs: A Systematic Review." *International Journal of Cardiology* 258: 279–88.
- Yu, G.C., Beresford, R. (2010). Implementation of a Chronic Illness Model for Diabetes Care in a Family Medicine Residency Program. *J GEN INTERN MED*, 25(4), 615–619. doi.org/10.1007/s11606-010-1431-9 <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11606-010-1431-9>
- Yu, G.C., Beresford, R. (2010). Implementation of a Chronic Illness Model for Diabetes Care in a Family Medicine Residency Program. *J GEN INTERN MED*, 25(4), 615–619. doi.org/10.1007/s11606-010-1431-9 <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11606-010-1431-9>

